

Everyday Life Information Seeking: A Review

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The iconoclastic study of Reijo Savolainen in 1995 has added a novel concept in the field of information study, naming everyday life information seeking (ELIS). Since then, ELIS study has been continuously growing in the different hands of different scientist employing different kinds of data gathering techniques like Critical Incident method, Focus group interview and Micro-moment time-line interview etc. Since the study focuses on people's non-occupational information seeking practice, the data gathering techniques have, hitherto, been very carefully handled keeping in mind that people's actual inclination to different sources and channels in ELIS should be minutely and accurately observed. However, there are some areas like ELIS of people with special needs, ELIS of illiterate people have yet to be touched and studied. The present study aims to find the knowledge gap in ELIS study already done up to now and suggest further research areas basing on a thorough study of almost 300 full text research articles pertaining to ELIS study.

Keywords: Information, Everyday Life Information, Information Seeking, Everyday Life Information Seeking, Critical Incident Technique, Coping, Print Media, Electronic Media

1 Introduction

Reijo Savolainen has recently been awarded the ASIS&T SIG USE 2008 Award for Outstanding Contributions to Information Behaviour with the publication of his seminal, iconoclastic work titling "Everyday Information Practices: A Social Phenomenological Perspective" that reads much like a "journal article with literature review, conceptual framework, study methods, results, conclusions and discussion" (Agosto, 2008) presented in basically that order. According to Savolainen, non-professional information seeking or everyday life information seeking (ELIS), as he prefers to call, of an individual is much influenced by the factors like leisure time, budget allocation, social capital and professional activities. Thus he is of the opinion that information seeking activities should be appropriately termed as "practice" (Savolainen, 1995) that pertains to habit instead of "behavior". Though everyday life information seeking treads in the field of

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library and information science, narrowly, in information organization and retrieval, it is not at all a new comer in the field of sociology, the systematic study of society, instead Berger and Luckmann in 1970s have critically analyses the everyday knowledge of the individuals in general and have fruitfully presents the "reality" (Berger & Luckmann, 1979) of everyday life "as subjective reality" and "objective reality" (Berger & Luckmann, 1979) and knowledge of everyday life as "common-sense knowledge" (Berger & Luckmann, 1979; Baert, 1998) to solve everyday life problems which establishes a similarity with the study of Savolainen (1995) when he promulgates that it is the "Mastery of Life" that guides a person's problem-solving and "specific" activities.

2 Objective

The objective of this study is to present an in-depth review of existing literature related to the previous researches on everyday life information seeking. To be precise, this review makes an endeavour:

- I) to locate lacunae or gaps in the development of the area;
- II) to identify aspects and facets that have either not been treated or treated insufficiently;
- III) to uncover methodologies that have already been used successfully by other researchers in the area;
- IV) to get new idea or approach on this area of investigation; and
- V) to develop a firmer understanding of the theoretical implications on this area of research.

3 Observations

The findings obtained from the review of relevant literature may be presented below.

3.1 Everyday Life

The information behaviors associated with daily life are extremely complex and cross many interests—parenting, entertainment, leisure, health and other concerns (Given, 2002). However, according to Savolainen (1995), the information seeking of any individual is two folds—job-related and non-work which is appropriately called everyday life information seeking which is also modified on a later time as everyday life information practice by its pioneer and promulgator. Thus, the phenomenological analysis of everyday life, or rather of the subjective experiences of everyday life, refrain from any causal or genetic hypotheses,

as well as from assertions about the ontological status of the phenomena analysed (Berger & Luckmann, 1979). People devote their most intensive attention to things which come close to everyday affairs and which belong to the world within actual reach or the primary zone of the life world such as home, family, and work (Scutz, 1964, p.123-127; Scutz and Luckmann, 1973, p.36-45). People always try to interpret the reality of everyday life with the information as well as knowledge he possesses. Here he in deciphering the reality uses 'commonsense knowledge' which is nothing but innumerable pre- and quasi- scientific interpretations about everyday reality (Berger & Luckmann, 1979). While scientists like Leckie, Pettigrew, & Sylvain's (1996) concentrate on the profession related information seeking of individuals, say, engineers, health care professionals, scientists like Savolainen takes individual's non-professional as well as non-work information seeking as a core area of activity since he believes that the informational activities of a person's everyday life comprise job-related and non-work type of information seeking and truly, the former has a keen impact on the latter in that the former shapes the scope for the latter. Human consciousness plays a significant role in deciphering the phenomena of the real world. Consciousness is always intentional and it always intends or is directed towards objects (Berger & Luckmann, 1979). Different objects present themselves to consciousness as constituents of different spheres of reality. One recognizes the fellowmen one must deals with in the course of everyday life as pertaining to a reality quite different from the disembodied figures that appear in one's dreams. This shapes a person's informational choices of sources in everyday life; his inclination towards media in everyday life and his particular actions in solving the problems-specific situations in everyday life (Berger & Luckmann, 1979; Savolainen, 1995; McKenzie, 2003); again, notably, everyday life information sources influence the choices of fiction books of the users of a public library in New Zealand (Ooi & Liew, 2011).

3.2 Information Needs and Seeking of Information

Need is a subjective experience that occurs only in the person in needs, and consequently, is not directly accessible to an observer (Wilson, 1997). Burnkrant (1976) defines 'need' as "a cognitive representation of a future goal that is desired". Morgan and King (1971) opine that needs emerge from three kinds of motives such as physiological motives, unlearned motives and social motives. Talking about the types of information needs, Weights et al. (1993) suggests three types which are (a) need for information; (b) need

to elucidate the information held; and (c) need to confirm information held. Chu and Law (2007) identify three stages of students' information needs which are general, specific and the current. Information seeking is a natural and necessary mechanism of human existence (Marchionini, 1992). It transcends the search for factual data to satisfy a gap in cognitive knowledge (Ooi & Liew, 2011). Therefore, seeking of information does not involve only the searching or browsing of factual data, instead it fetches the searching of conceptual or rather emotional (Ooi & Liew, 2011) data too. Kingrey (2002, p.1) proposes a more flexible definition of information seeking when he says "...information seeking involves the search, retrieval, recognition, and application of meaningful content". Information seeking can also be defined as the purposive acquisition of information from selected information carriers (Johnson, 1996, 1997). Wilson (1997, p. 562) postulates that information seeking processes implicitly take active searching as the principle mode as does Ellis's behavioural model of information seeking. He also asserts that two of the modes of "searching" of information can be appropriately termed as "acquisition" (Aaker, Batra & Myers, 1992). Individual information seeking has become a critical determinant of the success of organizational members and of the organization as a whole (Johnson, 2003). Taking the cue from the organizational perspectives, Johnson (2003, p. 737) affirms that individual information seeking becomes a pivotal force in explaining the handling of communication related to technical problems in an organization and in enhancing individual survival when they are confronted with a disease like cancer. While information seeking has been categorized in four ways as passive attention in which listening to radio or watching television programmes can be a means of acquisition of information though it is not happening intentionally; passive search that signifies those occasions when one type of search (or other behavior) results in the acquisition of information that happens to be relevant to the individual; active search where an individual actively seeks out information and ongoing search where active searching has already established the basic framework of knowledge, ideas, beliefs or values, but where occasional continuing search is carried out to update or expand one's framework (Wilson, 1997), Ooi and Liew (2011, p.749) opine that information seeking has two dimensions—a. information seeking in terms of what readers hoped to gain from reading fiction and b. information seeking in terms of what sources readers turned to, to find out about fiction books. The purpose of information seeking depends on, among other things, specific user needs and tasks at hand

(Kannampallil et al., 2012). While talking about the availability of information in information society, Karlsson et al. (2012, p. 577) make it clear that information seeking is no longer tied to physical facilities such as library buildings or bookstores and at present provision of information is rarely a problem. Information seeking of human beings have been studied from different spheres of life say from gender differences (Halder, Ray & Chakraborty, 2010), practices in everyday life (Savolainen, 1993), sense-making of the world (Dervin, 1992), situation based (Wilson, 1997), time as context (Savolainen, 2006), choice of fiction books (Ooi & Liew, 2011), application of common-sense knowledge to decipher the subjectivity and objectivity of reality (Berger & Luckmann, 1979), physicians in the intensive care unit (Kannampallil et al., 2012). Halder, Ray & Chakraborty put emphasis on the individual differences of information seeking. They have seen that the recognition of individual differences is increasingly becoming an important consideration in user information seeking studies (Dresang, 2005; Soloman, 2002; Tella, 2009) because undoubtedly, information seeking is a compelling area of research because of the various contextual forces currently affecting it (Johnson, 2003, p. 737) and different users adopt different strategies and tactics when seeking information (Tella, 2009). Searching Internet, particularly the World Wide Web has been the object of much research in recent years (Kari & Savolainen, 2007). Even it is now commonly agreed that information seeking is inextricably interwoven with context—they can be separated in scientific analysis, but not in real life (Sonnenwald & Iivonen, 1999). Different situations in the reality of everyday life pose different problems for the information seeking activities. Similarly, the distributed nature of information organization in critical care settings poses significant challenges for physicians in their information seeking activities including: (a) increased patient care time resulting from longer time for finding, filtering and organizing information due to the redundancy in available information and (b) increased possibility of missing information due to the distributed nature of information (Kannampallil et al., 2012). Savolainen (2006, p. 110) has noticed that time is one of the main contextual factors of information seeking.

3.3 Contexts as Information Seeking Method

Context which is specific situation in which communication occurs (Johnson, 1996) has become an important area of study for ELIS. Context means any background for information phenomena (Johnson, 2003). Context is all those

things which are not an inherent part of information phenomena but which nevertheless bear some relation to those. Without context, information phenomena lose their meaning. Context is social norms that enable us to understand how behaviors fit within the proper context of things as they are defined in a particular small world (Huotari & Chatman, 2001). Since individuals' daily non-work activities become a core area of study (Given, 2002), information seeking of individuals in the context of time (Savolainen, 2006); information needs in the contexts of social and individual (Given, 2002); health and particularly cancer related information seeking (Johnson, 2003); role of Internet in job related and non work information seeking (Savolainen, 1999); relationship between information seeking and context itself (Kari & Savolainen, 2007); and gender differences (Steinerova & Susol, 2007) and individual differences in information seeking (see e.g. Halder, Ray & Chakraborty, 2010) type of studies have been endeavored and came up with indisputably some novel findings.

3.4 *Everyday Life Information Seeking*

The concept of everyday life information seeking (ELIS) refers to the acquisition of various informational (both cognitive and expressive) elements which people employ to orient themselves in daily life or to solve problems not directly connected with the performance of occupational tasks (Savolainen, 1995). ELIS is a part of broader domain in library and information science (LIS) that focuses on human information behavior (HIB) (Spink & Cole, 2006a, 2006b). Like their colleagues in the cognate domain of information seeking in context (ISIC) (Vakkari, Savolainen, & Dervin, 1997; Wilson & Allen, 1999), ELIS researchers are concerned with situated users. The basic difference between them is that the ISIC researchers explore task and work environments, ELIS researchers focus on non-work contexts (Davenport, 2010) or "non-work information seeking" or "citizen information seeking" (Savolainen, 1995). The ways by which the individual monitors daily events and seek information to solve specific problems are determined by values, attitudes, and interest characteristics of their way of life (Savolainen, 1995) or the common-sense knowledge (Berger & Luckmann, 1979). While organizational information seeking has been a traditional focus of library studies, the everyday life information seeking (ELIS) movement (Savolainen, 1995), recently has focused attention on the variety of domains in which information seeking occurs in our day-to-day lives (Johnson, 2003, p.737). ELIS can be divided in two folds—seeking

of orienting information and seeking of practical information which serves as the solution to specific problems (Savolainen, 1995, p. 272). Hitherto, the seminal work or conceptual framework of ELIS method (Savolainen, 1995) has been a fundamental one for different kinds of studies like international students everyday life information seeking (Sin & Kim, 2013), young adults and everyday life information (Williamson et al., 2012), gaining access to ELIS (Carey, McKechnie & McKenzie, 2001), ELIS of university students and researchers (Given, 2002; Karlsson et al., 2012), relationship between information seeking and context (Kari & Savolainen, 2007), application of ELIS to explain organizational behaviour (Huotari & Chatman, 2001), time and internet (Savolainen, 1999) as an important context of ELIS (Savolainen, 2006), selection of fiction in public libraries as an impact of ELIS activities (Ooi & Liew, 2011). Agosto and Hughes-Hassell (2005, 2006a, 2006b; Hughes-Hassell & Agosto, 2007) investigated how urban teens (ages 14-17) look for information using ELIS framework of Savolainen (1995). However, sexual health information is a particular area of interest to adolescents. Howard (2006) and Howard and Jin (2007) explored the pleasure reading behavior of teenagers in Nova Scotia, Canada, reporting differences based on sex (girls read more fiction), the rising popularity of chain bookstores and self-reliance in selecting materials. Fisher and Landry (2007) investigated the information worlds of twenty (20) stay-at-home mothers who participated in multiple in-depth interviews and kept diaries over a three-week period. Westbrook (2007a, 2007b, 2008) focused on the information world of domestic violence survivors and library and other agency staff who work with them.

3.5 *Methods used in Everyday Life Information Seeking Studies*

Three commonly used methods in ELIS research are critical incident (CI) technique, focus groups, and the micro-moment time-line interview in sense-making methodology (SMM) (Davenport, 2010). Discourse analysis and ethnography as well as ethnomethodological studies are frequently applied in ELIS research (McKechnie, 2000; MacKenzie, 2004, 2006; Talja, 1997, 1999; Talja & MacKenzie, 2007; Williamson, 2006). Dialogic methods and everyday life studies have been coupled for many years (Davenport, 2010). Some of the recent trends of using various social science tools of different nature include standardized personality test from the Big Five personality model (John et al., 2008; Sin & Kim, 2013), structure equation modeling (SEM) (Sin & Kim, 2013) for data analysis, construct va-

lidity generalizations (Shadish, Cook, and Campbell, 2002; Sin & Kim, 2013), semi-structured interview schedule and demographic questionnaire (Williamson et al., 2012; Ooi & Liew, 2011; Lu, 2010), software like NVIVO (Williamson et al., 2012), NUD*IST 4 (Kari & Savolainen, 2007) for transcription of audio recordings and SAS (Lu, 2010) and SPSS (Dastforoush & Venkatesha, 2011) to perform statistical tests, transcribed think-aloud utterances (Karlsson et al., 2012, p. 579; Kari & Savolainen, 2007; Berg, Hoffman & Dawson, 2010), qualitative content analysis (Rich, 2002; Kari & Savolainen, 2007), in-depth qualitative interviews (Given, 2002), grounded theory (Given, 2002), small world theory (Chatman, 1991; Huotari & Chatman, 2001), 'Ethnograph' for theme decoding (Given, 2002), "open coding" (Lu, 2010), Mantel-Haenszel and Pearson's chi-square test, logistic regression (Lu, 2010), Spearman Correlation (Dastforoush & Venkatesha, 2011), empirical study using focused interview and critical incident technique (Savolainen, 1995), photo-diaics and photo-interviews (Keller, 2012), Tween Day involving scenario-based focus groups and interviews (Fisher et al., 2007; Meyers et al., 2007), mixed methods using keeping diaries (Niemela & Huotari, 2008).

3.6 Critical Incident Technique

The advent of critical incident (CI) technique (Savolainen, 1995) occurs in the literature in World War II in studies of air crews and their competence in specific material environments (Davenport, 2010). Despite many studies that claim to have a fundamental base of CI technique do not follow strictly the procedures required (Urquhart et al., 2003; Urquhart & Rowley, 2007). Flanagan (1954, p. 351) provides a detailed account of the history and procedures involved in this technique and clarifies that the aims of CI are to "solve practical problems" and "develop psychological principles" (p. 327). The critical incident technique, rather than collecting opinions, hunches, and estimates, obtains a record of specific behaviours from those in the best positions to make necessary observations and evaluation (Flanagan, 1954, p. 351). CI is a filtering technique for analyzing the confessional phenomena (Davenport, 2010). CI analysis is a method of establishing facts from qualitative data that is reliable only where safeguards are employed and this include member checking, triangulation (Fisher & Landry, 2007), and mindful selection of data (Flanagan, 1954). CI technique in ELIS should focus on a few clear topics such as health or employment (Savolainen, 1995).

3.7 Focus Groups

Like CI, focus group technique has also its genesis in World War II in the hand of Lazerfeld and Merton in 1941 (Davenport, 2010). Focus groups are an opportunity to observe informants conducting their own discursive tests, negotiating meanings, and confirming or disconfirming appropriate ways of speaking (Lunt, 1996, p.88). Focus group interviews were taken as a source of new ideas and hypotheses, not as demonstrated findings with regard to the extent and distribution of the provisionally identified qualitative patterns of response (Merton, 1987, p. 558). Researchers who use focus groups must make a number of important decisions at every stage of research project about design, sampling and analysis (Davenport, 2010). According to Lunt (1996, p. 85), "focus groups can be understood not by analogy to the survey...but as a simulation of those routine but inaccessible communicative contexts in which meaning is socially constructed in everyday talk." So focus groups are an admittedly approximate simulation of everyday talk/conversation and may be used in conjunction with, and in order to overcome, the disadvantages of other qualitative methods (Lunt, 1996, p. 85). However, this technique is not also perfect one but elicits some criticism that it fails to satisfy the validity and reliability conditions that characterize robust social science (Davenport, 2010). However, Dervin (2007), Meyers and colleagues (2007) recently presented focus groups as key technique for sense-making methodology (SMM).

3.8 Micro-Moment Time-Line Interviews

In sense-making methodology (SMM) the micro-moment time-line interview is the "core method" (Dervin, 1992, p. 70). Micro-moment time-line interview is suited to routine behavior and respondents are asked to focus on only one incident in this approach (Davenport, 2010). Since the starting point is a single "moment", participants can thus clarify or make sense of circumstances and actions that were formerly opaque or troubling (Davenport, 2010). However, the "gap-finding" and "gap-bridging" notion of SMM is under serious criticism when Savolainen (1993, p. 16) states that achieving generalizability "may not be easy because gap defining and gap bridging are contingent by nature depending on individual and situational factors." Savolainen (2006) also notes that SMM's lexicon and categorization techniques are problematic. Tuominen (1997, p. 367) observes that "user centered discourse does not necessarily liberate the user from the constraints of the system, and for

both librarians and users, there is no easy way out of the web of discursive power and the subject positions of an expert and a client that user-centered discourse offers to them.

3.91 Social Networks as Influential Factor in Everyday Life Information Seeking

Of late, there is rising interest in the use of social media in collaborative information seeking (Sin & Kim, 2013). Social question and answer (social Q&A) sites in particular have drawn notable attention (Gazan, 2011; Shachaf, 2010; Shah, Oh & Oh, 2009). With the rising popularity of social networking sites (SNS), as Sin and Kim (2013) notices, there is an upsurge of using these SNS in the benefit of people day-to-day activities. Yet, there is no such study of ELIS that particularly highlights people's ELIS, particularly the international students' ELIS in the light of SNS. Sin & Kim (2013) fill the knowledge gap by studying this and states that "SNS are of interest to international students' ELIS because they allow individuals to stay connected asynchronously with friends and family near and far since people are often rated as invaluable information sources (Agosto & Hughes-Hassell, 2005; Johnson, 2004). Therefore, friends on SNS can serve important informant role and provide useful everyday life information (Sin & Kim, 2013) being "social capital" (Savolainen, 1995). SNS can be conceptualized as being situated midway between (a) personal information exchanges in a rigid physical and psychological "small world" (Chatman, 1991), and (b) impersonal information retrievals over the vastly open Internet, as characterized by the popular adage, "On the Internet, nobody knows you are a dog" (Steiner, 1993) (Sin & Kim, 2013).

3.92 Information and Information Seeking Behavior

Being a citizen of information society, information is increasingly available to any person now (Aula & Nordhousen, 2006). In this present society, information seeking is no longer tied to physical facilities such as library buildings or bookstores. Information seeking is a "highly subjective process" (Weiler, 2005) influenced by many factors and interactions between them and these factors are related at least one of the three information seeking behavior core entities: the information need, the environment and the seeker (personal factors) (Marchionini, 1997; Wilson, 1981, 2006). Information behavior focuses on people's information needs (Wilson, 1997); on how they seek, manage, give, and use information, both purposefully and passively, in

the varied roles that comprise their everyday lives (Fisher & Julien, 2009). Information behavior includes both information seeking and communication. It can be described in terms of the activities of information users and providers, the factors affecting those activities and the sources or information products involved (Robson & Robinson, 2013). Case (2007) notes that information behavior is a broad field and the widest interpretation of it includes any paper that deals with information and people. "Human behavior in finding, using and communicating information is complex" (Robson & Robinson, 2013, p. 169). Ingwersen and Jarvelin (2005, p. 259) define information behavior as "generation, acquisition, management, use and communication of information, and information seeking". The study aptly shows that information seeking behavior forms a part of the whole that is information behavior. Studies on academic users' information searching behaviours can be divided into two research streams (Du & Evans, 2011) of which one is focused on understanding the micro-level characteristics of users' behavior, for example, information-seeking patterns (Ellis, 1993) and interactions with digital scholarly journals (Nicholas et al., 2006) and the other one is focusing on examining the impact of macro-level users' information behavior on library service like the studies of Rowlands and Nicholas (2008) and Maybee (2006). D'Alessandro et al. (2004) categorize the information seeking behaviours of general pediatricians into time spent on using computers, digital libraries and other information sources. Different scientists explore different areas of study with a huge variety of populations like international students' everyday life information seeking (Sin & Kim, 2013), young adults and everyday-life information (Williamson et al., 2012), context and information seeking in the light of Internet (Kari & Savolainen, 2007), gender differences in information seeking (Halder, Ray & Chakrabarty, 2010; Nicholas et al., 2010; Liu & Huang, 2008; Enochsson, 2005; Kennedy et al., 2003; Higgins & Hawamdeh, 2001; Gefen & Straub, 1997; Palmer, 1993;), non-linear principles of information behavior (Foster, 2005). Robson and Robinson (2013) note some key elements of information behavior such as Context, demographics, expertise and psychological factors, users' needs, providers' needs, motivating and inhibiting factors, and characteristics of information sources that form the crucial factors in the models of information and communication. However, Wilson (1997, p. 554) defines information seeking behavior in terms of stress and coping.

3.93 *Methods, Models and Theories in Information Behavior Research*

Though interviews form the main method (Fisher & Julien, 2011) of information behavior research, there are numerous modifications of it in the domain of information behavior research. Meta-analysis (Ankem, 2006), telephone surveys (Morey, 2007; Fisher et al., 2005), Observation (McKnight, 2007a, 2007b; Baker, 2004; Sonnenwald, 2006), log book keeping or journals (Pajarillo, 2007; Agosto and Hughes-Hassell, 2005, 2006a, 2006b; Fisher & Laundry, 2007), web surveys (Perrault, 2007; Bruce, Jones and Dumais, 2004), discourse analysis (Johannisson & Sundin, 2007; Carlisle, 2007; Olsson, 2005, 2007; Hedemark, Hedman & Sundin, 2005; Savolainen, 2007), conversation analysis (Nahl, 2007b), ethnographic methods (Williamson, 2006), "Tween Day Approach" (Meyers, Fisher & Marcoux, 2007). Growth and knowledge means growth of scientific theories (Vakkari and Kuokkanen, 1997). Activity theory is frequently applied in studying information seeking behavior. Bates (2005) thinks that models are most useful at the description and prediction stages of understanding a phenomenon. Amongst the numerous models developed to describe information behavior, those developed by LIS researchers tend to focus on information seeking rather than other aspects of information behavior (Robson & Robinson, 2013). The information seeking approach based on problem solving perspective of human behavior, has been the dominant approach within the field of library and information science (Spink & Cole, 2006). Some of the most important models of information behavior are Ellis' information seeking behavior (Ellis, 1989) based on empirical research, initially among social scientists, but subsequently tested on other groups such as academic researchers (Ellis, 1993), physicists and chemists (Ellis et al., 1993), engineers and scientists in an oil company (Ellis & Haugan, 1997), Kuhlthau's Information Search Process (ISP) (Kuhlthau, 1991, 2005) has been done on the school students initially and subsequently tested on lawyers (Kuhlthau & Tama, 2001) and securities analyst (Kuhlthau, 1999), Leckie et al. (1996) promulgates a general model of information seeking behavior, a comprehensive model of information seeking (CMIS) for the patients and others seeking of information about cancer (Johnson, 1997), health-related another model is that of Gorman's (1999), a cognitive model of Ingwersen and Jarvelin (2005), Wilson's models (1981, 1999; Wilson and Walsh, 1996), and information seeking and communication model (ISCM)(Robson & Robinson, 2013) amalgamating all these models.

3.94 *Bouncing in Information Seeking Behavior Research*

Bouncing as information seeking behavior (Nicholas et al., 2006) describes a form of behavior in which users view only a few web pages from the vast numbers available and generally do not return to the same website very often, if at all. The concept of 'willingness to return' was incorporated into the studies of digital reference and digital health information (Turner & Durrance, 2005). Bouncing behavior is clearly linked to browsing behavior.

3.95 *Everyday Life Information Sources and Channels*

A fundamental requirement for information-seeking is that some source of information should be accessible (Wilson, 1997, p. 561) and the lack of an easily accessible source may inhibit information seeking together (Savolainen, 1995; Wilson, 1997), or may impose higher costs than the enquirer is prepared to pay. Wilson (1997, p. 561-2) postulates that the sources of information are characterized by different factors like access, credibility, channels of communication. "Way of life" as order of things which is characteristic of certain social class gives only an overall picture of ELIS in that it tells how members of that social class tend to prefer various sources and channels due to their educational level and requirements of accumulating cultural capital (Savolainen, 1995, p. 289). Norman and Meischke (1991b) note that while doctors were the preferred information source for all types of health information there was, "compelling evidence that respondents perceived the utility of various sources very differently for different types of information". Connell and Crawford (1988) shows a rank order of information sources such as (a) print media; (b) television; (c) informal networks (friends, doctors); (d) radio; (e) organizations. Freimuth et al. (1989) finds that for authoritative information, people's preferences were (a) organizations; (b) family; (c) media. Again Toggerson (1981) asserts that where individuals were exposed to information from more than one channel, their information-seeking behavior increased. While describing about using of various information sources by physicians, it's been noted that many researches focus on the various sources of information that were used by clinicians to cater the information needs and these sources range from paper and electronic records, databases, research literature, professional colleagues or text books (Kannampallil et al., 2012; Davies & Harrison, 2007). D'Alessandro et al. (2004) argue that computer resources are the most "effective and time-efficient" mechanism for information seeking. Since the ad-

vent of Internet in the scenario of information using and accessing, all other traditional sources of information and channels seem stumble and "Internet is no longer a channel available only to a minor elite in universities and business enterprises" (Savolainen, 1999, p. 766). In choosing different media for accessing media as information sources, people make decisions on the basis of their "richness" and the choice of media is based on rational considerations of how well the qualities of a medium are expected to correspond to the substantial requirements of messages to be processed in communication (Savolainen, 1999, p. 767). The networked sources provided considerable help and in best case, the net search can provide the most economic way of finding a rapid and up-to-date answer to a specific problem (Savolainen, 1999). However, in his seminal work, Savolainen (1995) in an elaborative manner describes people's ELIS from different media basing on their class. Informants with relatively high level of education seek information more actively from various channels, for example, the public library (Savolainen, 1995, p. 289).

3.96 Print and Electronic Media

Printed media containing information in printed form is omnipresent even in this age of digital global village (Sharma, 2003). Of the many meanings of the word 'print' given by Merriam Webster's Collegiate Dictionary, the following is a list of the selected ones pertaining to the present study: (a) a mark made by pressure; (b) something impressed with a print or formed in a mold; (c) printed publications; and (d) to publish in print. The term 'printed media' includes books, magazines, newspapers, brochures (Sharma, 2003) and any other type of materials that confront to the process of printing. Many people regard newspaper reading as a significant source of accessing information in ELIS (Savolainen, 1995) and even the comparison of sources and channels of orienting information revealed that the newspaper, being a printed source of information, is as important as electronic media (Savolainen, 1995). While Keller (2012, p. 4) thinks that there are five categories of factors that influence the reader's choice between print and screen (electronic) media and these are attitudes, economic factors, physical healths and wellbeing, affordances and reader's engagement with text; Savolainen (1995), on the hand, asserts that people prefer the media of information basing on their "way of life" and "mastery of life". Electronic media are media that use electronics or electromechanical energy for the end-user (audience) to access the content. This is in contrast to static media (mainly print media), which today are most

often created electronically, but don't require electronics to be accessed by the end-user in the printed form (Wikipedia). In recent times, the role of the electronic services, in particular, the internet, has been given much attention in information seeking studies like job-related and non-work information seeking (Savolainen, 1999, p. 766) because the strengths of the electronic formats are based on the easiness of updating, modifying, or manipulating data, as well as on the rapid search ability of information from various sources (Savolainen, 1999). In comparison, the printed formats are superior in terms of high quality of printing, transportability and long tradition of use which is well rooted in the routines of everyday life (Ernest, 1993). Interactive media such as face-to-face discussion with contextually sensitive feedback mechanism are most functional in the case of ambiguous messages whereas static media such as memoranda are the poorest one (Savolainen, 1999). In an empirical study, Savolainen (1999, p. 767) finds that e-mail is the most appropriate tool in the transfer of information, communication of opinions, asking questions, keeping in contact with others and the creation of ideas (Savolainen, 1999). Savolainen (1999, p. 773) thinks the "seeking of orienting information manifested itself in the active monitoring of network sources (for example, reading of electronic newspapers). However, the electronic media elicits its criticisms too. The study of Gregory (2008, p. 269) reveals that although students liked the convenience, cost, and print-ability of e-books, they expressed concern with perceived eyestrain and reported confusion about certain navigation and search functions. Eyestrain and fatigue (Keller, 2012; Berger, Hoffman & Dawson, 2010), printing out (Keller, 2012; Spencer, 2006; Liu, 2006), distraction, lack of motivational effect of turning the page, breaking of traditional notion of owning a book and building a collection (Keller, 2012) are perhaps some noteworthy usability complaint from e-book users.

4 Conclusion

Though the incorporation of the term 'everyday life information seeking' occurs in LIS field with the hand of Savolainen in 1995 who made his iconoclastic empirical research basing on Pierre Bourdieu's "Way of Life" and "Mastery of Life", the ELIS study is not still in its infancy. There are so many novel findings emerging basing on ELIS framework. Context has become an important area of study of ELIS since ELIS is part of broader domain in LIS that focuses on human information behavior (HIB). Unlike other researchers of HIB, ELIS researchers tend to focus on non-

work contexts of information seeking employing, mostly, three techniques like Critical Incident, Focus Group and Micro-moment time-line interview with certain variations and modifications. Social networks are becoming influential factors in ELIS since they create an upsurge of 'social capital'. Bounded Theory, Rational Choice Theory, Information Ground Theory, Grounded Theory, Activity theory etc. are some of the most frequently used theoretical models of information and its seeking behavior studies including ELIS. However, there are some notable areas that require ELIS study in order to fill the knowledge gap and these are—a. ELIS of the people of twenty first century; b. ELIS of illiterate people; c. ELIS of the people with special needs; d. media inclination tendency of the present people through ELIS study; e. various types of ethnomethodological studies for ELIS; f. preference of sources and channels for information seeking in everyday life; g. social networking forming social capital as a major influential factor in ELIS etc. Moreover, the time has come to question whether "way of life" and "mastery of life" (Savolainen, 1995) are still deciding factors for ELIS of late, especially, after twenty years of its advent.

References

- Aaker, D.A., Batra, R., & Myers, J.G. (1992). *Advertising management*, 4th ed. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Agosto, D.E. (2009). Reviews. *Library and Information Research*, 31, 69-72.
- Agosto, D.E., & Hughes-Hassell, S. (2005). People, places, and questions: An investigation of the everyday life information-seeking behaviours of urban young adults. *Library and Information Science Research*, 27, 141-163.
- Agosto, D.E., & Hughes-Hassell, S. (2006a). Toward a model of the everyday life information needs of urban teenagers, part 1: Theoretical model. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 57, 1394-1403.
- Agosto, D.E., & Hughes-Hassell, S. (2006b). Toward a model of the everyday life information needs of urban teenagers, part 2: Theoretical model. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 57, 1418-1426.
- Ankem, K. (2007). Information-seeking behavior of women in their path to an innovative alternate treatment of symptomatic uterine fibroids. *Journal of the Medical Library Association*, 95(2), 164-172.
- Aula, A., & Nordhausen, K. (2006). Modeling successful performance in web searching. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 57(12), 157-175.
- Baert, P. (1998). *Social theory in the twentieth century*. UK: Polity Press.
- Baker, L.M. (2004). The information needs of female police officers involved in undercover prostitution work. *Information Research*, 10(1).
- Bates, M.J. (2005). An introduction to metatheories, theories, and models. In Fisher, K.E., Erdelez, S., & McKechnie, L. (Eds.). *Theories of Information Behaviour*. Information Today. Medford, NJ.
- Berger, P. & Luckmann, T. (1979). *The Social construction of reality*. Great Britain: Penguin Books.
- Berg, S.A., Hoffmann, K., & Dawson, D. (2010). Not on the same page: Undergraduates' information retrieval in electronic and print books. *The Journal of Librarianship*, 36(6), 518-525.
- Bruce, H., Jones, W., & Dumais, S. (2004). Information behavior that keeps found things found. *Information Research*, 10(1).
- Burnkrant, R.E. (1976). Amotivational model of information-processing intensity. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 3, 21-30.
- Carey, R.F., McKechnie, L.E.F., & McKenzie, P.J. (2001). Gaining access to everyday life information seeking. *Library & Information Science Research*, 23, 319-334.
- Carlisle, J. (2007). Digital music and generation Y: Discourse analysis of the online music information behavior talk of five young Australians. Paper presented at CoLIS: Sixth International Conference on Conceptions of Library and Information Science, Borås, Sweden.
- Case, D.O. (2007). *Looking for information. A survey of research on information seeking, needs, and behavior*, 2nd ed. San Diego, SA: Academic Press.
- Case, D.O., Johnson, J.D., Andrews, J.E., Allard, S.L., & Kelly, K. (2004). From two-step flow to the Internet: The changing array of sources for genetics information seeking. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 55(8), 660-669.
- Chatman, E.A. (1991). Life in a small world: Applicability of gratification theory to information-seeking behavior. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science*, 42, 438-449.

- Chu, S.K., & Law, N. (2007). Development of information search expertise: Research students' knowledge of source types. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, 39(1), 27-40.
- Connell, C.M., & Crawford, C.O. (1988). How people obtain their health information: A survey in two Pennsylvania counties. *Public Health Reports*, 103, 189-195.
- Dastforoush, M.T., & Venkatesha, Y. (2011). Dependency on electronic and print journals: A case study. *SRELS Journal of Information Management*, 48(4), 441-448.
- Davenport, E. (2010). Confessional methods and everyday life information seeking. *Annual Review of Information Science and Technology*, 44, 533-562.
- Dervin, B. (1972). From the mind's eye of the 'user': The sense-making qualitative-quantitative methodology. In J.D. Glazer, & R.R. Powell (Eds.), *Qualitative research in information management* (pp. 61-84). Englewood, CO: Libraries Unlimited.
- Dresang, E.T. (2005). The information-seeking behavior of youth in the digital environment. *Library Trends*, 54(2), 178-196.
- Ellis, D. (1989). A behavioural approach to information retrieval system design. *Journal of Documentation*, 45(3), 171-212.
- Ellis, D. (1993). Modeling the information-seeking patterns of academic researchers: A grounded theory approach. *Library Quarterly*, 63(4), 469-486.
- Ellis, D., Cox, D., & Hall, K. (1993). A comparison of the information seeking patterns of researchers in the physical and social sciences. *Journal of Documentation*, 49(4), 356-369.
- Ellis, D., & Haugan, M. (1997). Modeling the information seeking patterns of engineers and research scientists in an industrial environment. *Journal of Documentation*, 53(4), 384-403.
- Enochsson, A. (2005). A gender perspective on Internet use: Consequences for information seeking. *Information Research*, 10(4).
- Feinman, S., Mick, C.K., Saalberg, J., & Thompson, C.W.N. (1976). A conceptual framework for information flow studies. In S. Marin (Ed.), *Proceeding of the 38th Annual Meeting of the American Society for Information Science (ASIS)* (pp. 1-10). Washington, DC: ASIS.
- Fisher, K.E., & Julien, H. (2009). Information behavior. *Annual Review of Information Science and Technology*, 43(1), 7-73.
- Fisher, K.E., & Landry, C.F. (2007). Understanding the information behavior of stay-at-home mothers through affect. In D. Nahl & D. Bilal (Eds.), *Information and Emotion: The emergent affective paradigm in information behavior research* (pp. 211-234). Medford, NJ: Information Today.
- Fisher, K.E., Marcoux, E., Meyers, E., & Landry, C.F. (2007). Tweens and everyday life: Preliminary findings from Seattle. In M.K. Chelton & C. Cool (Eds.), *Youth information seeking behaviours: Context, theories, models and issues* (Vol. 2, pp. 1-25). Lanham, MD: Scarecrow.
- Flanagan, J.C. (1954). The critical incident technique. *Psychological Bulletin*, 51, 327-358.
- Foster, A.E. (2005). A non-linear model of information seeking behavior. *Information Research*, 10(2).
- Freimuth, B.J., Stein, J.A., & Kean, T.J. (1989). *Searching for health information: The Cancer Information Service Model*. Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press.
- Fulk, J., Schmitz, J.A., & Steinfield, C.W. (1990). A social influence model of technology. In J. Fulk, & C.W. Steinfield, *Organizations and communication technology* (pp. 117-141). Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Gazan, R. (2011). Social Q&A. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 62, 2301-2312.
- Gefen, D., & Straub, D.W. (1997). Gender differences in the perception and use of e-mail: An extension to the technology acceptance model. *MIS Quarterly*, 21(4), 389-400.
- Given, L.M. (2002). The academic and the everyday: Investing the overlap in mature undergraduates' information-seeking behaviors. *Library & Information Science Research*, 24, 17-29.
- Gorman, P. (1999). Exploring the contexts of information behavior. In Wilson, T.D., & Allen, D.K. (Eds.), *Information seeking of primary care physicians: Conceptual models and empirical studies. Proceedings of the Second International Conferences on Research in Information Needs, Seeking, and Use in Different Contexts*. Sheffield, UK.
- Haglund, L., & Olsson, P. (2008). The impact of university libraries of changes in information behavior among academic researchers: A multiple case study. *Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 34(1), 52-59.
- Halder, S., Ray, A., & Chakrabarty, P.K. (2010). The International Information & Library Review, 42, 242-251.

- Hedemark, C., & Hedman, J., & Sundin, O. (2005). Speaking of users: On user discourse in the field of public libraries. *Information Research*, 10(2).
- Heinstrom, J. (2003). Five personality dimensions and their influence on information behavior. *Information Research*, 9(1). Retrieved from <http://information.net/ir/9-1/paper165.html>
- Higgins, S.E., & Hawamdeh, S. (2001). Gender and cultural aspects of information seeking and use. *New Review of Information Behaviour Research*, 2, 17-28.
- Howard, P.N. (2004). Embedded media: Who we know, what we know, and society online. In P.N. Howard, & S. Jones (Eds.), *Society online: The Internet in context* (pp. 1-27). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Howard, V. (2006). Teens and pleasure reading: A critical assessment from Nova Scotia. Paper presented at the Canadian Association of Information Science Annual Conference, Toronto, Ontario.
- Howard, V., & Jin, S. (2007). Teens and pleasure reading: A critical assessment from Nova Scotia. In M.K. Chelton & C. Cool (Eds.), *Youth information seeking behaviours: Contexts, theories, models and issues* (Vol. 2, pp. 133-163). Lanham, MD: Scarecrow.
- Huotari, M.L., & Chatman, E. (2001). Using everyday life information seeking to explain organizational behavior. *Library & Information Science Research*, 23, 351-366.
- Ingwersen, P., & Jarvelin, K. (2005). *The turn: Integration of information seeking and retrieval in context*. The Kluwer International Series on Information Retrieval. Dordrecht: Springer.
- John, O., Nauman, L., & Soto, C. (2008). Paradigm shift to the integrative Big-Five trait taxonomy: History, measurement, and conceptual issues. In O.P. John, R.W. Robins, & L.A. Pervin (Eds.), *Handbook of personality: Theory and research* (pp. 114-158) (3rd ed.). New York, NY: Guilford Press.
- Johannisson, J., & Sundin, O. (2007). Putting discourse to work: Information practices and the professional project of nurses. *Library Quarterly*, 77(2), 199-218.
- Johnson, J.D. (1996). *Information seeking: An organizational dilemma*. Westat, CT: Quoron Books.
- Johnson, J.D. (1997). *Cancer-related information seeking*. Cresskill, NJ: Hampton Press.
- Johnson, J.D. (2003). On contexts of information seeking. *Information Processing and Management*, 39, 735-760.
- Kannampallil, T.G., Franklin, A., Mishra, R., Almoosa, K.F., & Cohen, T. (2012). Understanding the nature of information seeking behavior in critical care: Implications for the design of health information technology. *Artificial Intelligence in Medicine*. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.artmed.2012.10.002>
- Kari, J., & Savolainen, R. (2007). Relationships between information seeking and context: A qualitative study of Internet searching and the goals of personal development. *Library & Information Science Research*, 29, 47-69.
- Karlsson, L., Koivula, L., Ruokonen, I., Kajaani, P., Antikainen, L., & Ruismaki, H. (2012). From novice to expert: Information seeking processes of university students and researchers. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 45, 577-587.
- Keller, A. (2012). In print or on screen? Investigating the reading habits of undergraduate students using photo-diaries and photo-interviews. *LIBRI*, 62, 1-18.
- Kennedy, T., & Wellman, B., & Klement, K. (2003). Gendering the digital divide. *IT and Society*, 1(5), 72-96.
- Kies, J.K., Williges, R.C., & Rosson, M.B. (1998). Coordinating computer-supported cooperative work: a review of research issues and strategies. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science*, 49(9), 776-791.
- Krikelas, J. (1983). Information-seeking behavior: Patterns and concepts. *Drexel Library Quarterly*, 19(6), 5-20.
- Kuhlthau, CC. (1991). Inside the search process: Information seeking from the user's perspective. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 42(5), 361-371.
- Kuhlthau, CC. (2005). Kuhlthau's information search process. In Fisher, K.E., Erdelez, S., & McKechnie, L. (Eds.), *Theories of Information Behaviour*. Information Today. Medford, NJ. 230-234.
- Kuhlthau, CC., & Tama, S.L. (2001). Information search process of lawyers: A call for 'just for me' information services. *Journal of Documentation*, 57(1), 25-43.
- Leckie, G.J., Pettigrew, K.E., & Sylvain, C. (1996). Modelling the information seeking of professionals: A general model derived from research on engineers, health care professionals and lawyers. *Library*

- Quarterly, 66(2), 161-193.
- Lin, K.Y., & Lu, H.P. (2011). Why people use social networking sites: An empirical study integrating network externalities and motivation theory. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 27, 1152-1161.
- Liu, Z. (2006). Print vs. electronic resources: A study of user perceptions, preferences, and use. *Information Processing and Management*, 42(2), 583-592.
- Liu, Z., & Huang, X. (2008). Gender differences in the online reading environment. *Journal of Documentation*, 64(4), 616-626.
- Lu, Y.L. (2010). Children's information seeking in coping with daily-life problems: An investigation of fifth-and sixth-grade students. *Library & Information Science Research*, 32, 77-88.
- Lunt, P. (1996). Rethinking the focus group in media and communications research. *Journal of Communication*, 46(2), 79-98.
- Merton, R.K. (1987). Focussed interviews and focus groups: Continuities and discontinuities. *Public Opinion Quarterly*, 51(4), 550-566.
- MacKenzie, P.J. (2004). Positioning theory and the negotiation of information needs in a clinical midwifery setting. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 55(8), 685-694.
- MacKenzie, P.J. (2006). Mapping textually mediated information practice in clinical midwifery care. In A. Spink & C. Cole (Eds.), *New directions in human information behavior* (pp. 73-92). Dordrecht, The Netherlands: Springer.
- Malliari, A., Korobili, S., & Zapounidou, S. (2011). Exploring the information seeking behavior of Greek graduate students: A case study set in the University of Macedonia. *The International Information & Library Review*, 43, 79-91.
- Marcella, C. (2001). The need for European Union Information amongst women in the United Kingdom: results of a survey. *Journal of Documentation*, 57(4), 492-518.
- Marchionini, G. (1992). Interfaces for end-user information seeking. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science*, 43, 156-163.
- McKechnie, L. (E.F.). (2000). Ethnographic observation of preschool children in the public library. *Library & Information Science Research*, 22, 61-76.
- McKenzie, P.J. (2003). A model of information practices in accounts of everyday life information seeking. *Journal of Documentation*, 59(1), 19.
- McKnight, M. (2007a). Affective dimensions of critical care nurses' informative interactions: Gentle nurse Jekyll and harried nurse Hyde. In D. Nahl & D. Bilal (Eds.), *Information and emotion: The emergent affective paradigm in information behavior research and theory* (pp. 121-133). Medford, NJ: Information Today.
- McKnight, M. (2007b). A grounded theory model of on-duty critical care nurses' information behavior: The patient-chart cycle of informative interactions. *Journal of Documentation*, 63(1), 57-73.
- McQuail, D. (1994). *Mass communication theory. An introduction* (3rd ed). London: Sage.
- Meyers, E.M., Fisher, K.E., & Marcoux, E. (2007). Studying the everyday information behavior of tweens: Notes from the field. *Library & Information Science Research*, 29, 310-331.
- Morey, O.T. (2007). Health information ties: Preliminary findings on the health information seeking behavior of an African-American community. *Information Research*, 12(2).
- Morgan, C.T., & King, R.A. (1971). *Introduction to psychology*, 4th ed. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Nahl, D. (2007) A discourse analysis technique for charting the flow of micro-information behavior. *Journal of Documentation*, 63, 323-339.
- Nicholas, D., Huntington, P., Jamali, H.R., & Watkinson, A. (2006). The information seeking behavior of the users of digital scholarly journals. *Information Processing and Management*, 42(5), 1345-1365.
- Niemela, R., & Huotari, M.L. (2008). Everyday life information behavior. In M.L. Huotari & E. Davenport (Eds.), *From information provision to knowledge production. Proceedings of the International Conference for the Celebration of the 20th Anniversary of Information Studies*, Faculty of Humanities, University of Oulu (pp. 141-160). Oulu, Finland: University of Oulu.
- Olsson, M. (2007). Power/knowledge: The discursive construction of an author. *Library Quarterly*, 77, 219-240.
- Ooi, K. & Liew, C.L. (2011). Selecting fiction as part of everyday life information seeking. *Journal of Documentation*, 67(5), 748-772.
- Pajarillo, E.J.Y. (2007). Nursing information behavior (NIB) in the

- context of help-seeking. Paper presented at the Canadian Association of Information Science Annual Conference, Montreal, Quebec.
- Palmer, J. (1993). Scientist and information: Using cluster analysis to identify information style. *Journal of Documentation*, 47(2), 105-129.
- Perrault, A.M. (2007). An exploratory study of biology teachers' on-line information seeking practices. *School Library Media Research*, 10.
- Raacke, J., & Bonds-Raacke, J. (2008). Myspace and Facebook: Applying the uses and gratifications theory to exploring friend-networking sites. *Cyberpsychology & Behavior*, 11 (2), 169-174.
- Rieh, S.Y. (2002). Judgement of information quality and cognitive authority in the web. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 53, 145-161.
- Robson, A., & Robinson, L. (2013). Building on models of information behavior: Linking information seeking and communication. *Journal of Documentation*, 69(2), 2013.
- Roy, M., Taylor, R. & Chi, M.T.H. (2003). Searching for information on-line and off-line: gender differences among middle school students. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 29, 229-252.
- Rowlands, I., & Nicholas, D. (2008). Understanding information behavior: How do students and faculty find books?. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 26(5), 323-328.
- Rubin, A.M. (1994). Media use and effects: a uses-and-gratifications perspective. In J. Bryant, & D. Zillmann, *Media effects. Advances in theory and research* (pp. 417-436). Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Savolainen, R. (1995). Everyday life information seeking: Approaching information seeking in the context of "way of life". *Library & Information Science Research*, 17, 259-294.
- Savolainen, R. (1999). The role of the internet in information seeking: Putting the networked services in context. *Information Processing and Management*, 35, 765-782.
- Savolainen, R. (2006). Time as a context of information seeking. *Library & Information Science Research*, 28, 110-127.
- Savolainen, R. (2007). Media credibility and cognitive authority. The case of seeking orienting information. *Information Research: An International Electronic Journal*, 12 (3). Retrieved from <http://informationr.net/ir/12-3/paper319.html>.
- Scutz, Alfred (1964). *Collected papers II. Studies in social theory*. The Hague, Holland: Martinus Nijhoff.
- Scutz, Alfred & Luckmann, Thomas (1973). *The structures of the life world*. Evanston, IL: Northwestern University Press.
- Shachaf, P. (2010). Social reference: Toward a unifying theory. *Library and Information Science Research*. 32, 66-76.
- Shadish, W.R., Cook, T.D., & Campbell, D.T. (2002). *Experimental and quasi-experimental designs for generalized causal inference*, Boston, MA: Houghton Mifflin.
- Shah, C., Oh, S., & Oh, J.S. (2009) Research agenda for social Q&A. *Library and Information Science Research*, 31, 205-209.
- Sin, S.J., & Kim, K. (2013). International students' everyday life information seeking: The informational value of social networking sites. *Library & Information Science Research*. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.lisr.2012.11.006>
- Solomon, P. (2002). Discovering information in context. In B. Cronin (Ed.), *Annual Review of Information Science and Technology*, 36, 229-264.
- Sonnenwald, D.H., & Iivonen, M. (1999). An integrated human information behavior research framework for information studies. *Library and Information Science Research*, 21(4), 429-457.
- Spencer, C. (2006). Research on learners' preferences for reading: From a printed text or from a computer screen. *Journal of Distance Education*, 21(1), 33-50.
- Spink, A., & Cole, C. (2006a). Human information behavior: Integrating diverse approaches and information use. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 57(1), 25-35.
- Spink, A., & Cole, C. (Eds.) (2006b). *New directions in human information behavior*. Dordrecht, The Netherlands: Springer.
- Steiner, P. (1993). On the Internet, nobody knows you're a dog. *The New Yorker*, 69.
- Steinerova, J., & Susol, J. (2007). Users' information seeking behavior: a gender perspective. *Information Research*, 12(3). Retrieved September 28, 2010, from <http://informationR.net/ir/12-3/paper320.html>.
- Talja, S. (1997) Constituting "information" and "user" as research objects: A theory of knowledge formations as an alternative to the infor-

information man-theory. *Information Seeking in Context: Proceedings of an International Conference on Research in Information Needs, Seeking and Use in Different Contexts*, 67-68.

Talja, S. (1999). Analyzing qualitative interview data: The Discourse analytic method. *Library & Information Science Research*, 21(4), 459-477.

Talja, S., & MacKenzie, P.J. (2007). Editors' introduction: Special issue on discursive approaches to information seeking in context. *Library Quarterly*, 77, 97-107.

Tella, A. (2009). Correlates of undergraduates information-seeking behavior. *College and Undergraduate Libraries*, 16(1), 1-19.

Toggerson, S.K. (1981). Media coverage and information seeking behavior. *Journalism Quarterly*, 58, 89-93.

Tuominen, K. (1997). User-centered discourse: An analysis of the subject positions of the user and librarian. *Library Quarterly*, 4, 350-371.

Turner, T.C., & Durrance, J.C. (2005). Willingness to return. In K.E. Fisher, S. Erdelez, & E.F. McKechnie (Eds.), *Theories of information behavior* (pp. 382-386). Medford, NJ: Information Today.

Urquhart, C., Light, A., Thomas, R., Barker, A., Yeoman, A., Cooper, J., et al. (2003). Critical incident technique and explication interviewing in studies of information behavior. *Library & Information Science Research*, 25(1), 63-88.

Urquhart, C., & Rowley, J. (2007). Understanding student information behavior in relation to electronic information services: Lessons from longitudinal monitoring and evaluation, Part 2. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 58, 1188-1197.

Vakkari, P., & Kuokkanen, M. (1997). Theory growth in information science: Applications of the theory of science to a theory of information seeking. *Journal of Documentation*, 53(5), 497-519.

Vakkari, P., Savolainen, R., & Dervin, B. (Eds.). (1997). *Information seeking in Context: Proceedings of an International Conference on Research in Information Needs, Seeking and Use in Different Contexts*. London: Taylor Graham.

Weigts, W., Widdershoven, G., Kok, G., & Tomlow, P. (1993). Patients' information seeking actions and physicians' responses in gynaecological consultations. *Qualitative Health Research*, 3, 398-429.

Weiler, A. (2005). Information-seeking behavior in Generation Y students: motivation, critical thinking, and learning theory. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 31(1), 46-53.

Westbrook, L. (2007a). Community information networks for domestic violence survivors: Gaps and safety-nets. Paper presented at Library Research Seminar IV, London, Ontario, Canada.

Westbrook, L. (2007b). Surviving domestic violence: Seeking support in cyber-space. *Proceedings of the 18th Information Resources Management Association International Annual Conference*, 1294-1296.

Westbrook, L. (2008). E-government support for people in crisis: An evaluation of police department Web site support for domestic violence survivors using 'person-in-situation' information need analysis. *Library and Information Science Research*, 30, 22-38.

Williamson, K. (2006). Research in constructivist framework using ethnographic techniques. *Library Trends*, 55(1), 83-101.

Williamson, K., Qayyum, A., Hider, P., & Liu, Ying-Hsang. (2012). Young adults and everyday-life information: The role of news media. *Library and Information Science Research*, 34, 258-264.

Wilson, T.D. (1994). Information needs uses: Fifty years of progress. In B.C. Vickery (Ed.), *Fifty years of information progress: A journal of Documentation review* (pp. 15-51).

Wilson, T.D. (1997). Information behavior: An interdisciplinary perspective. *Information Processing and Management*, 33(4), 551-572.

Wilson, T.D. (2000). Human information behavior. *Informing Science: The International Journal of an Emerging Trans-discipline*, 3(2), 49-56. Retrieved September 28, 2010, from <http://www.inform.nu/Articles/Vol3/v3n2p49-56.pdf>.

Wilson, T.D., & Allen, D.K. (Eds.). (1999). *Exploring the contexts of Information Behaviour: Proceedings of the Second International Conference on Research in Information Needs, Seeking and Use in Different Contexts*. London: Taylor Graham.